
Research Article

Lectotypification of *Panicum mesocomum* Nees and a new combination in *Urochloa* (Poaceae)

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Abstract: A new combination is proposed for *Panicum mesocomum* Nees under *Urochloa* P.Beauv. as *Urochloa mesocoma* (Nees) R.Kr.Singh. To fix the application of the name and prevent misapplication, a lectotype is designated for *Panicum mesocomum* Nees.

Keywords: *Brachiaria mesocoma*, Lectotype, *Leucophrys mesocoma*, Namaqualand, South Africa

Introduction

Recent molecular phylogenetic studies have resulted in major changes to generic concepts, delimitation and classification within the family Poaceae. Based on the currently accepted and stable circumscription of the genus *Urochloa* P.Beauv. (Soreng et al., 2022), a new combination is proposed for *Panicum mesocomum* Nees under *Urochloa*. To ensure nomenclatural stability and avoid misapplication of the name, a lectotype is designated for *Panicum mesocomum* Nees. No holotype was indicated in the protologue and the name has not been typified previously. The lectotypification follows the guidelines and recommendations of Article 9 of the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Turland et al., 2025).

New combination

Urochloa mesocoma (Nees) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Panicum mesocomum* Nees, Fl. Afr. Austral. III. 34. 1841. *Leucophrys mesocoma* (Nees) Rendle, Cat. Afr. Pl. [Hiern] 2: 194. 1899. *Brachiaria mesocoma* (Nees) A.Camus, Bull. Soc. Bot. France 77: 640. 1931.

Figure 1: Lectotype of *Panicum mesocomum* Nees (S14-5521, © Swedish Museum of Natural History, Stockholm)

Figure 2: Isoelectotype of *Panicum mesocomum* Nees (K000281973, © The Trustees of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew)

Lectotype (designated here): South Africa, Northern Cape Province, Klein Namaqualand, Gariiep river near Verleptpraam, below 500 ft., 17 September 1830, *J.F. Drège* 2537 (S14-5521!, Figure 1); isolectotypes BM000923212!, HAL0082547!, K000281973! (Figure 2), L1273933!, P00442112!, S14-5524!, TUB006450!, US00148297!, W0021497!, W18890236314!.

Distribution: Angola, Namibia and South Africa.

Notes: *Panicum mesocomum* was described by Nees (1841) based on the specimens collected by *J.F. Drège* from Klein Namaqualand, South Africa. Eleven original specimens collected by Drège from this region were traced (BM000923212, HAL0082547, K000281973, L1273933, P00442112, S14-5521, S14-5524, TUB006450, US00148297, W0021497 and W18890236314). Among these, specimen S14-5521 is well preserved and conforms closely to the protologue, and it is therefore designated here as the lectotype. The collection date and number are mentioned only on the Paris specimen (P00442112).

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